

A Study Predicting the Orthodontic Treatment Need and Demand of Patients Visiting the Orthodontic Department: A Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Nowadays, orthodontic treatment demand increased in most countries. Therefore, rational planning of orthodontic measures on a population basis is essential to achieve comprehensive data on the prevalence of malocclusions and the social need for orthodontic therapy. So, the aim of our study is to explore how much of the variance in treatment demand could be explained by a set of self-assessed measures, and how these measures relate to professionally assessed treatment need.

Method: This descriptive, cross-sectional questionnaire-based survey with a sample size of 300 is conducted among an aged group of above 13 years who had visited in our department of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics, faculty of dental science. The main questionnaire consists of a total 18 closed-ended questions, which include a set of self-assessed measures dealing with self-esteem, such as dental and global self-esteem, various aspects of malocclusion, such as perceived malocclusion and perceived functional limitation, and treatment demand. Treatment need was assessed by the Dental Health Component of the Index of Orthodontic Treatment Need grading. This is assessed by the Chi-square test.

Results: The results showed that no significant differences between genders were found for the treatment demand and IOTN grades. The prevalence of professionally assessed treatment need, based on IOTN-DHC grades 3 (42.7%) and grade 4 (33.7%). The reliability of the scale score was good among all variables except prioritising healthy and straight teeth (.139).

Conclusion: The findings of the present study indicate that assessment of orthodontic treatment need would benefit from incorporating measures that evaluate patients' perceptions. Furthermore, the present study would display the unique effect of each included measure on clinical need and desire, and improve more cost-efficient predictions of treatment need and demand.

Keywords: Malocclusion, Index of Orthodontic Treatment Need (IOTN), Patient perception

INTRODUCTION

Malocclusion is defined as “an appreciable deviation from ideal occlusion.” Malocclusion is one of the most common oral pathologies, ranked third in world public dental disease priorities, next to dental caries and periodontal disease.^{1,2} Prevalence of malocclusion within the population has been an important tool in orthodontic diagnosis and treatment planning procedures. Achieving an optimum occlusal relationship is the first objective of orthodontic treatment.

The demand or self-perceived need for orthodontic treatment, particularly among adolescents, is on the rise in many countries. However, not all malocclusions need to be treated. An individual wants to improve, facial, dental and smile appearance for aesthetic concerns.³ This is the main reason for seeking orthodontic treatment is dissatisfaction with dental aesthetics, functional, social and psychological concerns. Therefore, it seems important to explore the psychosocial aspects of malocclusion and self-perceived need for treatment more widely.

Several indices have been introduced to evaluate the outcome of orthodontic treatment need, to select the patients who should be treated and establish priorities when resources are limited. The Index of Orthodontic Treatment Need (IOTN), described by Brook and Shaw⁴ in 1989, has been gaining national and international recognition as a method of objectively assessing treatment need because of its reliability and reproducibility. It is easy to learn, allowing rapid recording of relevant features and has been modified to guarantee greater reliability, especially when used by non-specialists in oral health surveys.

The IOTN index may be applied both clinically and to study casts. It consists of a dental health component and an aesthetic component. The dental health component (DHC) uses a 5-grade system with clear-cut points between the grades, with the most severe trait identified being the basis for grading the individual's need for treatment on dental health grounds. The aesthetic component (AC) consists of a 10-point scale, illustrated by a series of numbered photographs that show different levels of dental attractiveness. The value gives an indication of the patient's treatment needs on the grounds of aesthetic impairment.

Thus, the present study aimed to explore how much of the variance in treatment demand is explained by a set of self-assessed measures dealing with self-esteem and different aspects of malocclusion (questionnaire-based) and how these variables relate to professionally assessed treatment need (based on data from dental records) using the IOTN index.

METHODOLOGY:

This descriptive, cross-sectional questionnaire-based survey with a sample size of 300 was conducted among an aged group of individuals above 13 years who had visited our department of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics, faculty of dental science. The approval of the institutional review board (IRB) and the patient's consent to participate had been obtained to obtain the data for this questionnaire-based cross-sectional study. The questionnaire was prepared in English & a local language (Gujarati).

Data Collection: The Power of the sample was decided by the statistician and 300 forms were obtained. The patients who visited the department of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics were given the questionnaire. The patient's consent was taken before participation in the study. The main questionnaire consists of a total of 18 close ended questions, which included a set of self-assessed measures dealing with self-esteem, such as dental and global self-esteem, various aspects of malocclusion, such as perceived malocclusion and perceived functional limitation, and treatment demand. Treatment need was assessed by the Dental Health Component of the Index of Orthodontic Treatment Need grading. The distributed questionnaire had 18 questions based on a five-point Likert like response scale ranging from 0 to 4 format, and it was mandatory to answer all questions.

Study Design

A self-designed closed-ended offline questionnaire.

Study Duration

The data was collected between 1st March 2024 to 31st June 2024. A total of 300 filled questionnaires were collected to assess the data.

Selection Criteria

- Patient's age above 13 years
- Patient with no congenitally missing teeth
- No past orthodontic treatment experience

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patient's age below 13 years
- Incomplete forms were not included in the study.
- Questionnaires submitted after the timeline.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

SPSS version 25.0 was used for statistical analysis. The Pearson chi-square test assessed the association between orthodontic treatment need and demand. Mean values, standard deviations, and Cronbach's alpha were calculated to evaluate reliability. Pearson's correlation was used to analyze relationships between variables.

RESULTS

The total number of responses was 300, and the results of our study are as follows:

The final data set comprised complete responses from 300 individuals (58% girls). The prevalence of professionally assessed treatment need, based on IOTN-DHC grades 3 and 4, was 42.7 and 33.7 percent (Table 1 and Figure 1). The present study showed that the reliability of the scale scores was good except for perceived functional limitation ($\alpha = 0.162$), which can be considered satisfactory (Table 2).

IOTN Grade			
		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Grade 1	24	8.0
	Grade 2	47	15.7
	Grade 3	128	42.7
	Grade 4	101	33.7
	Total	300	100.0

Table 1: The prevalence of professionally assessed treatment need, based on the IOTN-DHC index.

Figure 1: The prevalence of professionally assessed treatment need, based on the IOTN-DHC index.

Measure	Question	Mean	SD	No. of items	α	Inter-item r
Psychological and social (Q)						
Dental self-esteem	Q1	2.61	.787	2	-1.842	.800
	Q2	1.73	1.158			.828
Global self-esteem	Q3	2.96	1.092	2	-0.463	.856
	Q4	2.18	1.119			.813
Social influence	Q5	2.09	1.138	3	-0.352	.853
	Q6	2.37	1.131			.823
	Q7	1.13	.850			.688
Malocclusion-related (Q)						
Perceived malocclusion	Q8	1.51	1.126	3	-1.165	.872
	Q9	2.66	1.027			.911
	Q10	1.71	1.395			.860
Perceived functional limitation	Q11	.65	.846	3	0.162	.764
	Q12	1.18	.893			.778
	Q13	3.00	.793			.556
Prioritising healthy and straight teeth	Q14	2.96	.956	2	-0.868	.794
	Q15	1.81	1.279			.807
Treatment demand and need						
Treatment demand	Q16	2.11	1.084	2	0.983	.968
	Q17	2.03	1.019			.962
Treatment need	Q18	2.25	1.41	-	-	-

Table 2: Basic statistics for the questionnaire-based (Q) and dental record-based measures (R).

Further analyses examined the correlations among all measures (Table 3). These correlations varied between 0.505 (social influence with global self-esteem) and a moderate correlation of 0.289 (Perceived malocclusion with treatment demand). Notably, the correlations among variables measuring similar or theoretically related constructs were high, supporting the construct validity of the measures. For example, global and dental self-esteem and perceived malocclusion and perceived functional limitations were highly correlated.

Measure	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Dental self-esteem	1							
Global self-esteem	.505**	1						
Social influence	-.245**	-.550**	1					
Perceived malocclusion	-0.061	-.142*	.369*	1				
Perceived functional limitation	0.078	.289**	.271*	.164*	1			
Prioritising healthy and straight teeth	.203**	.158**	-0.073	0.081	.379*	1		
Treatment demand	-.288**	.289**	-0.062	.462**	.168**	-0.077	1	
Treatment need (DHC)	-0.26* 0.64*	0.06	0.01	0.47*	0.17*	0.08	0.65*	-

Table 3: Intra correlations between measures

DISCUSSION

The present study proved that the constructed measures were reliable and related to treatment need as well as treatment demand. The results also revealed that treatment demand and treatment need were highly correlated. Further, the conducted study showed that treatment demand is largely explained by perceived malocclusion and dental self-esteem, which in turn are linked together and explained by perceived functional limitation, social influence and global self-

esteem. Further, treatment need was predicted by perceived malocclusion, which in turn was predicted by perceived functional limitation and dental self-esteem. Our research illustrates that the measures presented are not only linked together but also significantly linked to treatment need as assessed by orthodontists.

Here, we found a high zero-order correlation between the two measures ($r = 0.65$). Correlation of such a magnitude shows that professionally assessed orthodontic treatment need is predicted well by self-assessed treatment demand. This suggests the need for reflecting patients' perspectives in a similar area of research, as previously discussed study⁵. Additionally similar analysis conducted by J. Taghavi Bayat et al⁶(2017) found that correlation between the two measures ($r = 0.64$) and 33% of the variance in treatment demand and 22% of the variance in treatment need.

The current research was conducted in the age group of above 13 years old. They were able to independently answer the questionnaires and make a decision on the improvement of aesthetics and self-perception of demand for orthodontic treatment. This age group was considered adequate since orthodontic treatment with fixed appliances is often implemented at the age of 12–14 years, when all the permanent teeth have erupted. But also, since a certain level of psychological maturity is needed when responding to items, for instance, related to psychological variables. Earlier studies also indicate that children usually need to have reached an age of 13–14 years in order to achieve adequate reasoning about aesthetics in relation to orthodontics^{7,8}.

The results of our conducted study are also linked to dental record data concerning IOTN, being the official index for assessment of need for subsidised orthodontic treatment in the county of interest. The prevalence of treatment need, IOTN-DHC grades 3 and 4, in our study population was 42.7% and 33.7 % respectively. The present finding supported that the IOTN had relatively predictive accuracy for treatment need judgments that corresponded with demand for orthodontic treatment. This result corresponded with previous studies^{9,10}. This could be compared to prevalence rates of 21.3–39.5 percent reported in numerous European countries^{10,11}. A similar variation has been reported within the county councils of Sweden concerning commenced subsidized orthodontic treatment¹². Further, the proportion of individuals receiving orthodontic treatment based on dental records was 21%. Analyses showed that the proportion of participants

receiving treatment in this study was not significantly different ($z = 1.13$, $P = 0.26$) from figures presented earlier, 24%, concerning Uppsala County¹⁷. Given the above-mentioned factors, the study population is considered to be representative and the treatment need figures to be fairly reliable.

However, when it comes to IOTN as well as other morphological indices for treatment need prioritization, a systematic review in 2005 concluded that evidence for conclusions concerning their validity ‘are lacking’. Further study has been done in 2014 which stated that ‘most of the outcomes used in orthodontic research are concerned with measuring morphologic changes of treatment and do not reflect patient perspectives’¹³. Together with our findings this highlights that orthodontic treatment need assessments should be based on the consequences of malocclusion for the individual. Therefore, we suggest that, as a complement to the clinical evaluation and diagnosis, validated self-assessment measures ought to be used in a much higher degree than is the case today.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the present study indicate that assessment of orthodontic treatment need would benefit from incorporating measures that evaluate patients’ perceptions. Furthermore, present study would display the unique effect of each included measure on clinical need and desire, improved more cost-efficient predictions of treatment need and demand.

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